

A quantum entangled fractal superfluid universe

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Abstract: The cosmological redshift, the expansion of the universe, the origin of cosmic rays including the microwave background is set in context to a fractal superfluid universe. Quantum entanglement is explained by highly correlated components of quadratic maps of curvature which captures growth of organic matter as well conductivity plateaus in layer structures. A mechanism of controlled ultra-high energy emission is discussed. A fractal superfluid universe model is capable to solve the cosmological constant problem Dirac monopole problem and the phenomenon of quantum entanglement for unified forces.

1. Introduction

Gravitational field equations allow to regard stress-energy $T_{\mu\nu}$ as an equilibrium fluid or superfluid state [1]. From the viewpoint of coupling constants unified dimensionless fields as non-equilibrium, dimensionless states are capable to cover energy ranges of $10^2 \dots 10^3$ of orders of magnitude [2]. In macrophysics a pseudo-congruence on energy scale above 10^{20} eV as a fractal resolved potential difference explains the phenomenon of quantum entanglement (QE) for unified fields [3]. A fractal unified field allows to shift the origin of cosmic rays (CR) to a local bifurcating spacetime which explains also redshift and expansion of the universe by the influence of simplest cycles to vacuum susceptibilities. Experiments concerning the cosmological constant problem (CCP), QE and the Dirac monopole (DM) seem to prevent a unified theory of all forces [4] [5] [6]. Quantum statistics value (QS) ρ_{QS} of vacuum energy ρ_{vac} hundreds of orders of magnitude greater than experiment (CCP). Contrary, QS measures QE as a spooky action at distance. The origin of CR is an open problem which is shifted to galactic forces. The present paper explains e.g. air ionization measurements in vegetation areas by a bifurcating spacetime as a non-equilibrium fractal zeta universe (FZU). Action \mathcal{L} in Equation (3) is minimized for simplest cycles of chaotic quadruples of shifts $q_{sc}=\{1, \delta_k, \delta_k\delta_k, \delta_k\delta_k\delta_k\}$ as $q_{sc}\mathcal{L}=0$ whereas for an elastic continuum only $\delta_k\mathcal{L}=0$. In an open system ultra-high tensile forces envelope matter different from elastic fields. Accordingly, a large cloud mass generation dominates over a big bang scenario. Diurnal variations of ion concentrations as well as seasonal variations of CR count rates confirm a quantum entangled superfluid universe in Section 10. A cosmic-ray-charge-cloud-superfluid (FZU) resolves CCP, QE as well DM by a bifurcating spacetime with k-pseudo-congruences [2, 7]. The origin of QE is a k-component pseudo-congruent curvature as an alternating current between capacitor-like layers. The heat energy gain arises from superfluid layer-temperature vs. altitude-entropy changes as a Carnot process in Section 9. The origin of charge and mass by Feigenbaum renormalization using Hieb's hypothesis is an open problem [8] [9]. Hieb' conjecture $2\pi\delta_F^2 \approx \alpha_F^{-1}$ already had accuracy $9.12 \cdot 10^{-4}$ with Feigenbaum constant δ_F and fine structure constant α_F which is refinable on entropy-surface-area $4\pi R^2 \approx g_1^{;g_n}$ by optimizing $g_1 + \dots + g_n$ [10] [11]. Experimental values of the vacuum energy density ρ_{exp} are 50 to 200 orders of magnitude smaller than the theoretical value ρ_{QS} of zero-point energy suggested by quantum statistics (QS). This disagreement constitutes the substantial problem of the cosmological constant (CCP) [6] [12]. However, high-precision nanostructure measurements are in good agreement with QS. DM requires a **B**-field line pole in the complex electromagnetic field $\mathbf{E}+i\mathbf{B}$ realized e.g. by a ball of segments as a large cloud (monopole) mass where the quadratic in mass interaction dominates over linear rest mass [5]. The aim of the present note is to describe meV semiconductor experiments to clarify both fundamental problems. Charge quanta are experimentally detected for a mass ratio 10^{20} between oil drop and electron [13]. Within a fractal zeta universe (FZU) of bifurcating spacetime the Millikan experiment (ME), the quantum Hall (QH) effect, atmospheric clouds and universe clouds are shown to be self-similar tight-binding models each of mass ratio $\approx 10^{20}$ extending Dirac's large number hypothesis [14] [2]. A tight-binding approach of a liquid state easily explains the quantized Hall conductivity [15]. Accordingly, a QH tight-binding model with measurement precision $\kappa_{BO}=10^{-5}$ requires a thermal background cloud potential mass equivalent V_T of Planck mass $M_p \approx 10^{-5}$ g [2]. Surprisingly, atmospheric clouds have a similar mass ratio with respect to

earth mass. A charge of small mass m_e floats in a quasi-homogeneous cloud of a large background mass M_p . A sequence of universe mass $M_u \simeq 10^{56}$ g to mass of solar system 10^{33} g (10^{24}), mass 10^8 g of a 10^9 m³ cloud of density 0.5gm^{-3} to earth mass of 10^{27} g (10^{19}), an oil drop mass 10^{-12} g to electron mass 10^{-30} g (10^{18}) contains its ratio in brackets as the fourth power κ_{BO}^4 of the Born-Oppenheimer parameter κ_{BO} . Opposed is a liquid cloud slushy mass 10^{-5} g surrounding an electron mass 10^{-30} g (10^{25}) as a correlated thermal potential V_T of path-ordered, non-dissipative, non-radiative flow lines. The Millikan experiment for an oil drop of 10^{-12} g has $\kappa_{\text{BO}} = 10^{-3}$. A tree mass ratio of a wood of $3 \cdot 10^3$ kg and leaf mass of 30kg is about 10^{-3} giving an uncertainty of 0,3. The Enhanced Vegetation Index (EVI) of plant growth displays plateaus between 0,2 and 0,6 for a 120-day cycle in [16]. Orbits of period-doubling k -components of a quadratic map alternate with a lap number l_ω of equivalent periods ω . Simplest cycles q_{sc} of iterated quadruples $k+3 \in \{k, k+1, k+2\}$ yield a bicubic bi spinor norm solving CCP. Nanostructure experiments and cosmological and global parameter are self-similar [2]. In Section 2 physical scales are introduced in the quadratic map of dimensionless curvature. Section 3 relates multi-dimensional action functionals to one-dimensional complex holomorphic functions like the Dirichlet L-function or the Xi-function. The physical motivation is that a closed one-dimensional complex contour is a curvature or time-thermal Carnot cycle as a base for stress-energy stability. Section 4 confirms Feynman diagram series for all interaction which are based on simplest cycles of iterated curvature. In Section 6 equivalence between the quadratic map and invariant substitutions of a quartic polynomial of curvature is seen in context of Friedmann equations. Inducible CR-emission is predicted by transitions between conductivity plateaus in QH in Section 7. QH plateaus are described as holomorphic leaves of a growing tree generating non-reversible Carnot cyclic clouds with quadratic -in-mass van der Waals-like interaction.

2. Unified field equations as simplest cycles

The quadratic map based FZU implies Lorentz-invariance by complex fixpoints of binary invariant substitutions $\gamma(\phi_3)$. In Hermite variables the universe radius $R_u = H(\phi_4)/48\phi_4$ enters the time integral of the Friedmann solution [17]

$$ct = \int \frac{\sqrt{R_u} dR_u}{\sqrt{\phi_3(R_u)}} \quad (1)$$

with Hessian $H(\phi_4)$ of a quartic polynomial ϕ_4 with $\Phi_n(t) = \sum_{i=0}^n a_i t^{n-i}$. A cubic invariant polynomial $\phi_3(R_u)$ implies discriminant changes $\Delta_3 \rightarrow \Delta_3 \phi_3^2$ under $\gamma(\phi_3)$ with $4H^3(\phi_3) + Q^2(\phi_3) + 27\Delta_3 \phi_3^2 = 0$ for invariant $Q \simeq g_3$, $H(\phi_3) \simeq g_2$. In FZU simplest cycle quadruples $q = \{1, \delta_k, \delta_k \delta_k, \delta_k \delta_k \delta_k\}$ are one addition step $k, k+1, k+2$ on elliptic curves with a linear relation between three polynomial coefficients a_i . This is equivalent to the singular case of a normal bicubic field $\mathbb{N}[(\sqrt{\Delta_2}) = \mathbb{K}[\partial] \mathbb{K}'[\partial] \mathbb{K}''[\partial]]$ with a square discriminant of a quadratic field $\Delta_2 = \square$. Discriminants are singular $\Delta_n = \Delta_2 = \Delta_3 = \Delta_4$. if the determinant of a $n^2 \cdot n^2$ dimensional matrix $q = (\hat{a} \otimes I - I \otimes \hat{a})^2$ vanishes [18]. This holds for a linear relation $a_{ij} - a_i j - a_i j = 0$ between three coefficients of \sqrt{q} , e.g. for $n=2$

$$\sqrt{q}_{ij} = \begin{vmatrix} 0 & -a_{12} & -a_{12} & 0 \\ -a_{21} & a_{11} - a_{22} & 0 & a_{12} \\ a_{21} & 0 & a_{22} - a_{11} & -a_{12} \\ 0 & a_{21} & -a_{21} & 0 \end{vmatrix} \quad (2)$$

\sqrt{q} is singular if $a_{11} - a_{22} - a_{12} = 0$. A three-component linear relation (10) appears for a quadruple of shifts $q = \{1, \delta_k, \delta_k \delta_k, \delta_k \delta_k \delta_k\}$. Then $c_k a_k + c_{k+1} a_{k+1} + c_{k+2} a_{k+2} = 0$ is a local process whereas Feigenbaum renormalization (9) proves the existence of a global pseudo-congruence for generator α_F . Eqs. (9-12) are valid for unified fields as a linear relation between each three coefficients $a_{ij} \in \{R, \Lambda, T\}$, $\{G, G_0, \Sigma\}$ or $\{P, P_0, \Xi\}$ which are regarded as functionals. A simplest cycle relation holds for general relativity. where $a_{ij} \simeq R, \Lambda, T$ imply the linear relation $4\Lambda - R = \kappa_4 T$ being the trace of Einstein field equations $R_{\mu\nu} - \frac{1}{2} g_{\mu\nu} R + \Lambda g_{\mu\nu} = \kappa_4 T_{\mu\nu}$. Regardless of the interaction a linear relation between three functionals is an irreducible Dyson equation for Greens function G and mass operator Σ or Bethe-Salpeter equation of P, P_0 and Ξ for polarization function P and vertex part Ξ [19]. Formally a quadratic map of universe radius $\gamma \circ R$ is complex curvature where γ is

proportional to a product of Green's functions in Equation (12). For open, closed or flat spacetime Feynman diagram series hold for quantum statistics, Einstein field equations and dark interaction in FZU. Time in the elliptic integral (1) is the Lebesgue measure for chaotic bifurcations which is a complex global integral $t+i\beta \simeq V+iV_T \simeq \omega$ (13).

3. Mass and energy in a dimensionless information-based universe

Information universe is accessible by binary substitutions γ giving rational coordinates. Complex γ -fixpoints are viewed as Lorentz-transformations which are complex γ . Modular and elliptic invariants $j(\omega)$, $\gamma_2(\omega)$, $\gamma_3(\omega)$ depend on $f(\omega)$. A Lorentz invariant $f(\omega)$ is a mass for powers f^3, f^8, f^{12} and f^{24} . The Legendre modular function $\lambda_\mu = \lambda_{\mu m} / m + 1/2$ gives e.g. a mass $m = 4/f^{12}(\omega)$ where $\lambda^2 - 1/4 = m^2$. The Dirac-like current density $\lambda_{\mu m} = \bar{\Psi}_q \lambda_{\mu m q} \Psi_{q'}$ is invariant for equivalent substitutions of ω which are called laps. Period-doubling bifurcating k -components of γ generate a tree of masses. Iterating the Weber invariant $f(\omega)$ is iterating over all possible masses in the universe. An iteration is like a quadratic transformation of periods ω where the Legendre modular function λ proportional to a coupling constant $\lambda \simeq G_w \rightarrow 0$ of invariances $\lambda, 1/\lambda, 1 - 1/\lambda, 1/(1-\lambda), \lambda/(1-\lambda), 1 - \lambda$. The Dirichlet L- function $L(1, \chi)$ is proportional to a circulant matrix in $-\hbar_\Delta R_\Delta / \sqrt{\Delta} = (12 \ln 2 + \ln \lambda + \ln(1-\lambda)) / 8\sqrt{\Delta} \simeq (12 \ln 2 - \lambda + \ln \lambda) / 8\sqrt{\Delta}$. For optimal units $f \rightarrow f + \ln f$ the L- function $L(1, \chi)$ is proportional to a coupling constant and to a mass. The FZU big bang scenario is self-similar to a 4-step-algorithmus to gravitational waves [20]. However, energy is gained by a thermal Carnot cycle. A quadratic in mass (moment of inertia, quadrupole moment Q) expansion transforms a Lorentz-invariant tree into resting, floating masses by the algorithm

$$(fixpoints\ of\ \gamma) \rightarrow \gamma(Lorentz-invariant) \rightarrow q_{sc} \rightarrow \psi_s \rightarrow Q_{ij}(three-dimensional\ \mathbf{v} \rightarrow 0)$$

where pair creation rest mass energy is overwhelmed by a quadratic van-der-Waals-like potential in the limit of an infinite number of quadrupolar constituents being momenta of inertia. Unobservable ultra-high energy particles above GZK cutoff are identified with k -components between tree root in z_{nt} and first v_{sh} at $k=3$. Doubling at logistic parameter $r \simeq 3.54 \simeq 4$ suggest a base 4 with Fermat number transforms. All k -components imply invariant elliptic addition steps with $\lambda g^2 \simeq G_w M_w^2 \simeq G_w H_w^{-2} \simeq inv$ with modular unit g , Hubble parameter $H_w = \delta_k \ln \varphi$, order parameter $\varphi \simeq K + iK'$, quarter periods K, K' , cloud masses M_w proportional to generators $M_w \simeq g$ and coupling constants (6). Interacting shells $w=1,2,3,4,5$ are invariant plateaus where vacuum density with $M_w \simeq H_w^{-1}$, i.e. $M_5 > \dots > M_1$ obeys

$$\rho_{vac} \simeq \frac{H_w^2}{8\pi G_w} \simeq \frac{H_4^2}{\kappa_4 c_l^2} \simeq \hbar c_l \simeq inv, \kappa_w \simeq \frac{8\pi G_w}{c_l^4}.$$

Nearly invariant addition on fluctuating elliptic curves in spacetime solves the cosmological constant problem with a w -independent mean vacuum density ρ_{vac} . Because the Hubble parameter H_w depends on k -components as $\ln 2^{2^k}$ the third branch $k=3$ yields a mean CMB energy density

$$\rho_{vac}^{CMB} \rightarrow \frac{H_3^2}{8\pi G_5 (2^{2^3})^2} \simeq \frac{\rho_{vac}}{2^4} \simeq \rho_{vac}^{CMB} (T \simeq 2,3K)$$

The relation between iterates, curvature and field tensor drawn in Section 7 allows to associate tree root k -components with CMB waves where periods v_{sh} act as an external alternating current. Because k -components fill out spacetime nearly isotropic even a dimensionless bifurcated spacetime concludes to 3K CMB of wavelength $1...10cm$ or frequency $1...10^3 GHz$ [21].

4. L-function regulator process

Irreducible dynamics in Section 6 is reducible to complex transformations of a holomorphic function $\xi(z \simeq \lambda)$ by (10) searching a relation between $\phi_3(f)$ and $\phi_3(R_u)$ in Equation (1). Spacetime points are cyclotomic or Kronecker-Weber extensions of a bicubic field. An irreducible dynamic creates a bifurcating k -component spacetime tree. Invariance $\gamma \circ \xi$ and $\gamma \circ z \xi(z = \lambda[f(\omega)])$ differs from iterating the modular invariant $\gamma \circ f(\omega)$. Note that $f_k^{24} \simeq 1/\lambda \lambda'$ is singular in λ_k where $z \simeq \lambda$. Simple $\zeta(z)$ -poles in $z \simeq \lambda$ are linked to simple $\zeta(z)$ -zeros by a certain different substitution $\gamma \circ z_{nt}$ which is regarded as a mass operator series. A holomorphic in $\lambda \xi(z = \lambda[f(\omega)])$ depends on curvature tensor $f(\omega) \simeq R_{\mu\nu} \simeq \mathbf{E}$ where $\xi(z = \lambda[f(\omega)]) \simeq \mathbf{E}$. Coordinates on Gaussian plane z or Riemann sphere are exactly linked with Dedekind zeta function $\zeta(z, \mathbb{K})$, Riemann zeta function, ξ -function and Dirichlet L- function $L(z, \chi)$

$$\frac{\zeta(z, \mathbb{K})}{\zeta(z)} = \frac{\Gamma(z/2)z(z-1)\zeta(z, \mathbb{K})}{2\pi^{z/2}\xi(z)} = L(z, \chi) \quad (3)$$

where $L(z, \chi) \simeq R_\Delta / \sqrt{\Delta}$ is proportional to a regulator $R_\Delta = R_{\Delta ij} = \ln_b E_{ij}$, for base b , fundamental unit E_{ij} and discriminant Δ of a cubic field. Iterates of $z \simeq \lambda$ depend on (10) where z_k is $f(\omega)$ -like and z_{k+1} is λ -like. Extension fields with r -dimensional lattices of cyclotomic units E_{ij} ($1 \leq i, j \leq r$) induce local minima of the L-function. A screened Poisson equation (4) couples via Equation (3) with Dirichlet-character χ conveyed through chaotic periods to the Artin L-function, the Dedekind zeta function $\zeta(z, \mathbb{K})$. A sum over ideal norm as a quadratic form yields the Epstein zeta function $\zeta(z, \mathbb{Q}[\sqrt{\Delta_k}])$ which depends via map $\gamma(\phi_3)$ on the hyperelliptic theta function $\vartheta(u_\pm)$. The L-function in (3) depends on a module norm function which depends on a power of the Dedekind eta function $\eta(\omega)$ [22]. The regulator process is stationary cycle $R_\Delta \simeq \mathcal{L}$ which takes lower values than for a given extension field [3]. Rational (real) coordinates imply a vanishing discriminant $\Delta \rightarrow 0$ (general relativity). The Minkowski bound prescribes either rational fields $\Delta = 0$ or cyclotomic limits $\Delta \rightarrow \infty$ in interpolating nontrivial zeros z_{nt} of $\xi(z)$ and $\zeta(z)$. Regarding two stripes $\pm \frac{1}{2} \pm im_n$ are as two capacitor plates a holomorphic entire function $\xi(z)$ yields a Poisson-like equation for λ -slices

$$Q(z) = \Delta_{xy} (L(z, \chi)\xi(z)) + \mu_s L(z, \chi)\xi(z) = \pm \mu_c (\text{Im} \lambda \pm m_n) \quad (4)$$

Holomorph $\xi(z) \simeq \mathbf{E}$ with $z = \lambda[\gamma \circ f]$ where $\Delta_h \xi(z) = 0$ with $\Delta_h = y^2 \Delta_{xy} = \text{Im} \lambda^2 \Delta_{xy}$ are called conductivity plateaus. An electric field-like $\xi(z)$ is subjected to a λ -process as a current. Lagrange condition (μ_s) in Equation (4) ensures a nontrivial zero $\xi(z_{nt} = \pm \frac{1}{2} \pm im_n) = 0$ as a screening process for invariant γ -orbits. Lagrange condition (μ_c) in Equation (4) ensures a finite charge to-mass ratio because λ depends on mass. Solutions $Q(z)$ of (4) are modified Bessel functions which are also entire. Four zeros $Q(z \simeq z_{nt} = \pm \frac{1}{2} \pm im_n)$ in (4) are related to a quadruple q_{sc} of steps. Gravitational waves result from q_{sc} where four-dimensions to a one-dimensional wave which is inverted here [20] [21]. The first $Q(z)$ iterate is a fourth-order differential equation $a\Delta_h + b\Delta_h \Delta_h = 0$ known from [23]. Subsequent iterations yield as 2^{2^k} quadrupolar ball of iterates $Q(z) \circ \dots \circ Q(z)$ which is entire and solves the two-dimensional Laplace equation Δ_h . FZU iterates $\gamma \circ z$ which represent a 2^{2^k} th order differential equation. This screened two-dimensional Poisson equation is invariant with respect to a simultaneous change $\gamma \circ z \simeq \gamma \circ \lambda$ and $\gamma \circ z_{nt}$. Zeros z_{nt} are certain values of λ . $\gamma \circ \lambda$ implies a quadratic equation for masses m_{nt} . This quadratic equation for masses holds for γ -invariant Kummer surfaces $K(X(\gamma \circ f(\omega)))$. Here $\gamma \circ f$ and $\gamma \circ z \in \mathbb{C}^w$ yield an underdetermined system of quadratic equations. A longitudinal, transverse and rotatory vicinity of an arbitrary point in a spherical-shell in \mathbb{C}^w has surface, altitude and volume components. Shells can be explained by a capacitor model. Locally, zeros of $\zeta(z_{nt})$ in capacitor plates-stripes $\pm \frac{1}{2}$ are condensation nuclei in five atmospheric spherical shells in \mathbb{C}^w . A permanent alternating current flow between capacitor plates due to seasonal and altitude variations is shown in Figure 1. The $L(z, \chi)$ -function gets a non-equilibrium regulator process with three constituents μ_1, μ_2, μ_3 in equation (12) under subsequent z -maps. These are a conductivity plateau (holomorphic equilibrium state), air ionization (net rate) and CR bifurcation (scattering). The regulator term μ_1 is an entire, holomorphic conductivity plateau. The term μ_2 is a count rate which is a non-equilibrium air

ionization rate proportional to a statistical occupation being the geometric zeta function $\zeta(l_s, m_s, z)$. The third term μ_3 is a scattering rate of occupation number changes as a bifurcation tree. Here k -components explain as well CMB and ultra-high CR shower. Inherent in any definition of a spacetime point is the uniqueness and invertibility which requires simple zeros z_{nt} of a complex holomorphic function. Multiple of z_{nt} are charge quanta which arise in pairs. Globally, a seasonal average counts the number of k -components as the number of particles as leaves of a tree. Locally, capacitor plates obey congruent alternating voltages $\text{mod}(2^{2^k} - 1)$ which explains the phenomenon of QE. The congruence is due to a renormalized Feigenbaum equation (9) where a second constant α_F proves the existence of a generator. Zeros z_{nt} are a singularity in the r.h.s of equation (4) as an alternating current for equivalent laps $\lambda(\gamma \circ f) = \lambda(f)$.

Figure 1: A second sound in quadropoly interacting z_{nt} : (Left) Long-wave (seasonal) motion, (Right) Short-wave motion with two stripes $z_{nt} = \pm \frac{1}{2} \pm im_n$ of the Riemann zeta function where stripes $\pm \frac{1}{2}$ are viewed as capacitor plates. A first and second sound in Figure 1 corresponds to a growth of a global binary tree of particles (leaves in seasonal variation) superimposed by local capacitor voltages as a CR- shower. Spacetime forms from a Carnot cycle of longitudinal, transverse and rotatory directions. In plant growth the EVI displays plateaus [16]. A charge in Equation (4) is the $k \rightarrow \infty$ limit of holomorphic leaves (plateaus) of neutral chaotic quadrupolar γ -simplest cycles in $\xi(z)$. The QH current is a neutral oscillating complex quadrupole (inertial) moment Q_{xy} . Experimental support for FZU is oscillation of the gradient of global temperature over 10^6 years (=plateaus of temperature) and microwave emission at QH [24] [25]. Detector dimensions for ME, QH and CR detector (Wulf's bifilar electrometer, Wilson chamber) and air ion count Gerdien condenser are comparable [26]. FZU predicts an invariant dimensionless vacuum energy density $\rho_{FZU} \approx \lambda_k g_k^2 \approx \rho_{exp}$ for a power tower of modular units g_k . Transitions between conductivity plateaus σ_H (leaf growth) induce CR emissions. The tight-binding model with $\kappa_{B0} \approx 10^{-20 \cdot \frac{1}{4}} = 10^{-5}$ of mass ratio 10^{20} displays potential changes as relative mass changes. A first prediction of high-energy emission at QH not yet observed is extended to a model of a universal CR-atmospheric charge cloud superfluid [27] [28]. Iterated Weber invariants $f(\omega)$ by map (10) is regarded as a complex curvature which is proven in Section 7. Doubly-periodic cycles v_{sh} due to Sharkovskii's theorem require two constants α_F, δ_F . Whereas laps l are stationary particle orbits k -components are a bifurcating shower of particles. Particles at first periods v_{sh} at $k \leq 3$ are not observable. Periods v_{sh} near $k=3$ is spacetime oscillation felt as cosmic microwave background (CMB). k -components changes into a fluid of elastic spacetime at step $k \approx G_5^{-1}$ with dark exchange scattering coupling constant $G_5 \approx 10^{-167}$. The most general Riemann surface $\binom{w+1}{2} < 3w+3$ for $w \leq 5$ induces a self-similar pseudo-congruence for $k \approx 2^{2^9}, 2^{2^{10}} \rightarrow 1$ due to an intersection between coupling constant in the regulator index and Legendre module $\lambda_k = 4q^{2^{k-1}}$ for period-doubling $\omega_k \rightarrow \omega_{k+1} + \omega_{k+2}$ as $\omega \rightarrow 2\omega$ with nome $q^{i\pi\omega} = e^{-\pi K'/K} \approx 2$ which is hidden in the existence of a second Feigenbaum constant α_F . FZU-emission rates of CMB at QH behave as κ_{B0}^{-2} . Regarding k -components as identical charges quantum statistics overestimates ρ_{exp} by factor $2^{2^k} \approx G_5^{-1}$ as a F_9, F_{10} -congruences with Fermat number F_t in $\rho_{QS} \gg \rho_{exp}$ [29].

5. Feynman diagram series for five interactions

A bi spinor ψ is defined as a simplest cycle quadruple of norm $(\sum_{(q)} E_q^{-2}) = \sum_{(s)} \psi_s \bar{\psi}_s$ averaged over laps valid for all interactions. QS sets a norm $\sum_{(s)} \psi_s \bar{\psi}_s = 1$ for all bifurcating 2^{2^k} CR air shower components which overestimates vacuum energy ρ_{vac} by the CCP-factor 2^{2^k} . In reality vacuum energy ρ_{vac} contains only rare ultra-high CR counts. FZU consists of cryptographic-like pseudo-random integer addition steps on elliptic curves. QS implies finite λ_k and g_k . Macrostructures imply $\lambda_k \rightarrow 0$ and large $g_k \rightarrow \infty$ for $k \rightarrow \infty$. Self-similarity implies invariance $\lambda, 1/\lambda, 1 - 1/\lambda, 1/(1-\lambda), \lambda/(1-\lambda), 1 - \lambda$. On the most general complex Riemann surface the cubic behavior of $f(\omega)$ transmits to λ and the coupling constant G_w for $w \leq 5$ interactions $w = (1-5) = (\text{strong, weak, em, grav, dark})$. A bicubic bi spinor norm $Nm(\psi) = E_i \psi' \psi'' = 1$ of conjugated units is capable to formulate an invariant energy density

$$\rho \simeq \frac{1}{2} \sum_{(w,k)} G_w(E) E(\mathbf{k}) \simeq \rho_{FZU} \simeq \rho_{exp} \simeq 10^0 \dots 10^{-1} \text{eVcm}^{-3} \simeq \rho_{CR} \simeq \rho_{CMB} \quad (5)$$

Within a dimensionless FZU energy $E(\mathbf{k})$ is defined as a change of units E_i or a change of λ_k related to k -components [2]. λ_k defines a Dirac equation where the wave vector \mathbf{k} is related to periods v_{sh} capturing Bloch states by $\gamma(\phi_3)$ - fixed points. CCP requires a cutoff due to $E(\mathbf{k} \rightarrow \infty) \rightarrow \infty$. QS implies v_{sh} congruent laps and k -incongruent components. FZU implies finite $E(\mathbf{k} \rightarrow \infty) \rightarrow E_\infty$ and predicts a congruence $2^{2^k} \rightarrow 1$ which lowers the vacuum energy. A coupling constant

$$\ln G_w(0) = -w! 2^w \ln_3 2 \quad (6)$$

results from a formerly constant regulator index $R_{\Delta ij} = \ln_b E_{ij}$ in Equation (14) optimized by circulant process. For dark matter at $w=5$ one has $G_5 \simeq 10^{-167}$. In QS the circulant behavior is reflected by a scattering process. For simplest cycles q_{sc} the Euclidean norm $(\sum_{(q)} E_q^{-2}) = \sum_{(s)} \psi_s \bar{\psi}_s$ in Equation (4) recovers the until now accepted bi spinor norm. The cutoff in Equation (5) is due to Equation (6) with energy-dependent coupling constant $G_w(E)$. Local minima of the L-function are stationary states. In macrophysics the unified bi spinor norm is a tidal-like state of four curvatures of four points. CCP is a time averaging problem for rare but ultra-large mass $M_k \simeq g_k$ on bifurcating clouds

$$\rho_{QS} \simeq \Delta t M_k c^2 R_{net} + \rho_{exp} \quad (7)$$

with $M_k \rightarrow \infty$ and $R_{net} \rightarrow 0$ depending on the four-dimensional volume of complex time $d\sigma_5$ for time interval $\Delta t \rightarrow \infty$. Number theoretic congruences $1 = 2^{2^k} \simeq G_5^{-1}$ resolve CCP by reducing ρ_{QS} to ρ_{exp} . As a result, CR and CMB occur in any bifurcating spacetime also at low altitude- atmospheric layers. In FZU the order parameter $\varphi \simeq K + iK'$ is linear expanded into complex curvature $R \simeq f(\omega)$. Elliptic curves represent themselves a self-similar system because quarter periods K, K' are exact theta constants. Complex scalar curvature $R = \gamma \cdot R_u$ produces bifurcating tensile forces as a prerequisite for stationary spacetime or balanced ionized CR- CMB clouds. Iterated complex $f(\omega)$ enter theta constants $\eta(\omega) f^2(\omega)$ which are equivalent to a correlated path-ordered complex temperature potential $V + iV_T$. Enveloping periods v_{sh} are explained by congruent integers a_k, b_k, Δ_k determining half-periods $\omega_i = \frac{1}{2}(a_k + b_k i \sqrt{\Delta_k})$ [2]. The most general Riemann surface includes added points on iterated elliptic curves as cryptographic, regular, pseudo-random chaotic period-doubling. Cubic roots $f(\omega)$ of $\phi_3(f(\omega))$ are iterated by

$$\gamma(\phi_3(f)) = \begin{vmatrix} \frac{1}{3} \phi_3'(f) & \phi_3(t) - \frac{f}{3} \phi_3'(f) \\ -1 & f \end{vmatrix} \quad (8)$$

In the context of the symbolic map (8) an orbit subgroup of equivalent lattices with $\text{dety} = 1$ is called lap of γ else a k -component. Laps as non-turbulent Carnot cycles v_{sh} of the thermal potential $V + iV_T$ accumulate a large neutral background cloud. This is enabled by quadratic-in-mass-excitations of large scale floating non-radiative bifurcations as a pre-stage of spacetime from a zero of a complex entire, differentiable function. The electric field-like holomorphic function $\xi \simeq E$

$$\xi(z) = \left(\frac{z}{2}\right) \pi^{-\frac{z}{2}} \Gamma\left(\frac{z}{2}\right) \zeta(z) = \frac{1}{2} \prod_n \left(1 - \frac{z}{z_n}\right) = -\frac{\partial j(z)}{\partial z}$$

is governed current-like

$$j(z) = -4 \int_1^\infty \frac{dt}{\log t} t^{-1/4} \partial_t (t^{3/2} \partial_t (\vartheta_3(0, e^{-\pi t}) - 1)) \sinh(1/2(z - 1/2)) \log t \text{ with Jacobi theta function } \vartheta_3 \text{ [30].}$$

Driven by $\gamma \circ f(\omega_k)$ and invariances $\gamma \circ z, \gamma \circ \xi(z)$ in Equation (4) are a universal clock frequency $j(z)$. Like zeros $z_{nt}=\lambda_k$ as quanta of charge Coulomb singularities appear for $f(\omega_k)[\lambda_{k+1}]$ generalizable to n-dimensions [21] [31].

6. The universe- a binary invariant (fractal) neutral superfluid potential flow

A relation of charge and flux to thermal convection has already been proven. The superconducting order parameter φ is a theta function [32]. Nonequilibrium electrons in semiconductors are capable for Benard convection [33]. Dynamics of Kirchhoff equations $X_{k+2}=\hat{a}[\gamma]X_{k+1}$ and $X_{k+1}=\hat{a}[\gamma]X_k$ of $X_k[f(\omega)] \in \mathbb{R}^3, \mathbb{P}^3$ on $K(X(f)), W(Y(f))$ is governed by SE(3) steps as discrete iterates (8) of invariants $f(\omega)$ with orthogonal transformation $\hat{a}[\gamma(f)]$. Iterated velocities of $X_k(f(\omega))$ are gradients $X_{k+1}-X_k=\nabla V_T$ of a non-turbulent potential flow (11 where period-doublings are new cubic roots. Map (8) creates an entire, holomorphic polynomial $f_k(f_{k=0})$ in $f_{k=0}$ which is singular in dependence on λ . At step $k=0$ a pole $f^2(\omega)|_{k=0}=2^4/\lambda(\lambda-1)$ exists on λ -plane of $\zeta(z=\lambda)$. Subsequent steps yield Feigenbaum renormalized invariants

$$z_k = -\alpha_F z_{2k} \leftrightarrow \gamma^{(\text{ren})}(z) = -\alpha_F \gamma^{(\text{ren})} \circ \gamma^{(\text{ren})}(-z/\alpha_F) \quad (9)$$

$$c_k z_k + c_{k+1} z_{k+1} + c_{k+2} z_{k+2} = 0 \leftrightarrow \gamma^{(\text{ren})} = \gamma + \gamma \circ \Gamma^{(\text{ren})} \circ \gamma^{(\text{ren})} \quad (10)$$

$$F(t, z) = \gamma(\phi_3(t)) \circ z \simeq \phi_3(t)/(t - z) - 1/3 \phi_3'(t) \quad (11)$$

$$F(t, z) \simeq A_\mu G_{ss''} \gamma_{s''s'''}^\mu G_{s''s'''} - 1/3 \frac{\delta A_\mu}{\delta(G_{ss''} \gamma_{s''s'''}^\mu G_{s''s'''})} \quad (12)$$

Accordingly, binary substitutions γ envelope Feynman diagram series of Dyson-like equation for a Greens function $G_{ss'}[\psi]$ defined in terms of a quartic roots shifted to $s=\pm\infty, \pm i\infty$ as q_{sc} [29] [3]. Optimal units $E(\omega_k)$ and $f_k=f(\omega_k)$ with Euclidean norm $\sum_q f_q^{-2} = \sum_q f_q' f_q''$ reproduce a bicubic spinor norm $Nm(f(\omega))=f(\omega)f'(\omega)f''(\omega)=2$ with complex conjugates invariants f' and f'' . Quantum statistics implies k-incongruent γ -orbits averaged over stable laps (seasons) in a binary tree. Equation (10) is solved by a tent map giving e.g. a Cantor set $\zeta(l_s, m_s, z)$ and in the limit $k \rightarrow \infty$ a complex Lebesgue measure dl_{xy}

$$V_{T_{global}} = \int \nabla V_{T_{cloud}} dl_{xy} \quad (13)$$

The complex line element $dl_{xy} \leftrightarrow du = dz/\sqrt{\phi_3} \leftrightarrow \gamma \circ dz/\sqrt{\phi_3}$ is iterated by eqs. (9-12). A high voltage measured between points on a straight line is resolved on a fractal line. Optimal entropy is given by minimizing the quadratic form of a circulant regulator $R_{\Delta ij}^2$ for finite geometric zeta function $\zeta(l_s, m_s, z)$ of string length l_s and multiplicity m_s and Euclidean norm $N(E) = (\sum_{(q)} E_q^{-2}) = \sum_{(s)} \psi_s \bar{\psi}_s$ as

$$2\mu_1 R_{\Delta ij} + 2\mu_2 \zeta(l_s, m_s, R_{\Delta ij}) e^{2R_{\Delta ij}} + \mu_3 N(e^{R_{\Delta ij}}) \zeta'(l_s, m_s, R_{\Delta ij}) = 0 \quad (14)$$

for an entropy-based universe [10]. A Mandelbrot zoom sequence first unrelated explains the Huygens-Fresnel principle by μ_1, μ_2, μ_3 superposed cardioids and zoomed bulbs of spheres-in-spheres information currents [2]. Equation (14) is solvable in complex four-dimensional space by a four-component complex rotations of units $E_i = \exp(i l_i)$. Local plateaus in (14) are $L(z, \chi)$ -function induced elastic Lagrangians.

7. Bi spinor as a classical particle

All forces are treated uniquely by Feynman diagrams for bi spinor $\psi_s \simeq f_s(\omega)$ with Euclidean norm $(\sum_{(q)} E_q^{-2}) = \sum_{(s)} \psi_s \bar{\psi}_s$. A bicubic $q_{sc} \psi_s$ is viewed as spacetime curvature $R_{\mu\nu} \simeq F_{\mu\nu} \simeq \mathbf{E}, \mathbf{B}$ governed by $z_{k+1} \leftarrow z_k^2 + c$ for

$z \simeq f(\omega)$ rewritten as a quartic polynomial $\mathbf{R}_{\mu\nu}^4 + 2\mathcal{F}\mathbf{R}_{\mu\nu}^2 - \mathcal{G}^2 = 0$ with $\mathbf{R}_{\mu\nu} = \text{Re}z_k$, $F = \frac{1}{2}\text{Re}(c - z_{k+1})$, $G = \frac{1}{2}\text{Im}(c - z_{k+1})$. A finite iterated set z_k with periods v_{Sh} can be projected onto complex plane as a generator g_k or a root of unity. Optimal coordinates appear in (14) for a tower $g_{k+1} \simeq \exp(ig_k)$ which interchanges wave vector and classical momentum as a classical particle. Universe anti-matter is defined as irreducible q_{sc} vertices 1,2,1'2' of a point as irreducible tidal motion. [7]

8. Conductivity plateau as a holomorphic leaf

A magnetic field $\mathbf{B} \simeq \delta_k h_t(g_k) \simeq (\text{days of the year})$ is equivalent to changes of topological entropy $h_t(g_k)$ and seasonal changes as days of the year. Then plant growth measured as EVI is equivalent to a QH conductivity plateau with thermoelectric field $\mathbf{E} \simeq \nabla T$ as gradient of temperature where a mass ratio 10^3 and accuracy 0,3 between wood and leaves. For $k \rightarrow \infty$ a universal coupling constant is expected resulting from an area $2\pi\delta_F^2$ corrected by a factor g_i^{gn} [8] [10]. The fine structure constant at high energies (high k values) exhibits a minimum e.g. $1/128$ at 10^9eV [34]. Similarly, a QH plateau describes a universal (all interaction containing) neutral quadrupolar current contained also in a definition of a bis spinor. Only a forest of trees with k -components of partial laps towards define a quantum of charge. The exosphere- earth-surface-capacitor state is a flowing congruent alternating current. The concept of charge is connected with alternating capacity changes of an ergodic treetop-root symmetry. The treetop-root system of the binary tree is asymmetric, non-ergodic, non-reversible and generates matter. This asymmetry is a quadrupolar-quadrupolar weak, nearly neutral capacitor state compatible with modular units and the Macdonald denominator formula. Here $\eta \binom{N-1}{2}$ is a product of theta functions $\prod_{1 \leq i < j \leq N} \vartheta_1(u_i - u_j, \omega)$ which is a Vandermonde determinant Δ_N for the simple Lie algebra A_{N-1} [35] [36]. A Vandermonde determinant is $\exp(|u|^2) \Pi(u_i - u_j)^N \simeq \exp(|u|^2) \Delta_N$ which is known as the Laughlin- wave function similar to N^{th} order Weierstrass sigma functions $\sigma^{(N)}(u, \omega)$ for arguments $u = a\omega$ [37] [38]. Standard units of time and energy count the number of precessions n and the number of Carnot cycles m independent on fluctuating ω . A floating tidal-like phase-correlated bifurcating fluid cloud persists with balanced collision-less ionization in a stable universe. The minimum $z_k \simeq V_T(f_k)$ allows rare ultra-high energy CR and persistent CMB of the iterated 2^{2^k} polar holomorphic fluid $z_{k+N}[\dots z_k]$ that forms a ball of string segments. A growing n -leaved tree as a 2^{2^k} quadrupolar ball due to a single zero z_{nt} opens the next zero point if all sites in \mathbb{C}^5 are occupied at $2^{2^k} \simeq G_w^{-1}$.

9. Second sound thermopower cycle

The cosmic-ray-charge-cloud (atmospheric) model is a capacitor-like chaotic RC oscillator which stores charge and mass. The resistance R in the circuit is the k -component congruence, the capacity is the number of nontrivial zeros and its frequency are the number of cycles v_{Sh} . The energy gain $VI \simeq V^2$ or $\simeq I^2 \simeq \Delta h_t \Delta T$ undergoes a quadratic map where the Carnot cycle area is $\Delta h_t \Delta T \text{dety}$. A one-dimensional zero of $\zeta(z_n) = 0$ is traversed by three-dimensional points $X_k(f)$ of a dissipation less superfluid in space with electric field $\xi \simeq \mathbf{E}(z) \simeq (\nabla V, \nabla V_T)$ composed from gradients of V and V_T . A closed loop in complex plane yields a holomorphic potential $V(z) = Q_S V_T(z)$ creates topological entropy h_t per charge carrier per z_{nt} via the Seebeck coefficient $Q_S = h_t / eN_e$. Physically a time-thermal Carnot cycle with two sounds(cycles) v_{Sh} and q_{sc} yields a voltage(energy) gain up to ultra-high-energies over 2^{2^k} components for $k > 8$.

10. global seasonal temperature cycle and local altitude entropy cycle

First and second sound in a Carnot cycle gains energy where one-dimension extends to three dimensions as shown in Section 3. Exact addition on fractal chaotic elliptic curves implies a sound within a sound or $v_{sh}[v_{sh}]$ recursively. Waves of universe radius R_u are waves of temperature $R_u \simeq K, K' \simeq \theta^2$ and entropy h_t . Longitudinal, transverse and rotatory motions $\mathbf{k}_i \mathbf{k}_j$, $\delta_{ij} - \mathbf{k}_i \mathbf{k}_j / k^2$, $\epsilon_{ijkl} \mathbf{k}_k \mathbf{k}_l$ are global seasonal temperature waves and local altitude entropy waves where handedness creates spin. A spinor $\psi_q = f(\omega)[\lambda] f(\omega)$ has a simple pole $1/\lambda\lambda'$ for each multiple $f^{24}(\omega)$ entering the measure dl_{xy} in the global temperature potential (13). A holomorphic gradient $\nabla V_T \simeq E(z) \simeq \xi(z)$ in $\lambda_k[f_k(\omega)]$ gets singular in $f(\omega)$. A certain iterate $f(\omega)$ in $\lambda\lambda' = 2^4/f^{24} = 1/4 - z_{nt}^2$ meets a zero z_{nt} . Four zeros $\pm 1/2 \pm im_n$ in V_T yield a three-dimensional quadrupole moment Q in $r_i Q_{ij} r_j / r^5 \simeq 1/r^3$. The thermal potential $V_T(\lambda)$ has a cubic, roton-like upper valley: In dependence on defining the velocity of light $c = 1/\sqrt{\epsilon\mu}$ by a vacuum permittivity $\epsilon_0(r) \simeq r^2$ or not one gets $V_T(\lambda) \simeq Q/\epsilon r \simeq Q/r^3 \simeq m r^2 / r^3 \simeq m/r$ either a quadrupolar potential V_Q or a Kepler-Coulomb-potential in unified space. The Fourier-component of V_Q contains a contact interaction term giving a bag potential which is compatible with a cubic behavior of coupling-constants. Iterations $Q(z) \circ \dots \circ Q(z)$ of the Poisson equation (4) form a 2^{2^k} polar cloud of segments. Segments resolve e.g. fractal a 10^{20} eV voltage into a minimal e.g. 1meV potential (13) and vice versa. Entropy changes are k-congruences and first sound, dl_{xy} are second sound and temperature waves in $V_{T_{global}}$ which are measured in Figure 9. The atmospheric equivalent of second sound is e.g. flash bang and thunder as independent thermal and entropy cycles of q_{sc} of an incompressible superfluid. The cubic invariant couples longitudinal and rotatory components in roton-like upper energy valleys [39] [40]. The Feigenbaum diagram is a hysteresis of a Carnot cycle.

11. Cosmic rays, cosmological redshift and microwave background in bifurcating spacetime

Energy in dimensionless scales is k-component and can range up to the GZK cutoff as the onset of first v_{sh} . [41]. In the vicinity of every point a big bang scenario is possible capable to create large cloud masses. Second sound is a quadrupolar wave inherent to spacetime as a background permeability $\epsilon_0(\mathbf{k}) = 1/I_{ij} \mathbf{k}_i \mathbf{k}_j$. The potential $1/\epsilon(\mathbf{k}) k^2$ corresponds to exchange scattering or permanent tidal waves of two objects. Its spatial dependence in $\epsilon_0(R_u) \simeq R_u^2$ explains the cosmological redshift. CMB is caused by the overall first appearance of v_{sh} in clock rate $j(z)$. CR emissions have low count rate $1/2^{2^k}$ but ultra-high energy. So far organic matter has been used for power plants. An associated CR generation causing air ionization has been ignored so far which could be controlled in nanostructures as a novel possible future energy technology. Its energy gain can be estimated by the T-h hysteresis area of Carnot cycles. Besides understanding climate, second sound is implicit in a model of a universe and concerns background susceptibilities with apparent expansion and redshift.

12. Comparison with existing experimental data

Rare CR of probability 2^{-2^k} cause enhanced anomalous atmospheric ionization (μ_2 -term), a changed air composition, nuclear disintegration stars in QH layers or plants. As a prerequisite for mass creation correlations over macroscopic dimensions in large scale CR detector arrays with a very low count rate up to 10^{-2} year are also a measure of stability. This holds also for organic matter where air ionization accompanies plant growth because of a partial small amount of matter created from nothing or matter canceled out by its negative field energy. Dimensionless Q_{xy} oscillations in Equation (4) are rather waves of the metric (gravitational waves). In form of CMB they indicate the stability of space. Accordingly, besides existing matter at plant growth matter plus radiation is created. The overall CMB is viewed as the part of

first k-component cycles of bifurcating spacetime. A seasonal variation of CR and temperature is an indication of a coupling to organic matter on earth and atmospheric clouds. The velocity of the second sound is proportional to the entropy $\delta_{kh} \approx \mathbf{B}$ and depends e.g. on magnetic field. QH microwave emission has been already detected [25]. As an indication low k-components $k \approx 1$ are capable to explain the CMB amount of 10^{-4} on vacuum energy ρ_{vac} . With increasing density of chaotic k-components quadratic and higher polynomial mass terms dominate the linear rest mass favoring growth of surrounding clouds or leaves. FZU favors creating large mass clouds near a nontrivial zero z_{nt} in distinction to a single-particle-big-bang-scenario. In FZU, existing particles serve as catalysts of an eternal non-equilibrium process or alternating capacitor state. Various experiments support FZU which have been previously classified differently. These include microwave emission at quantized conductivities, seasonal variations of cosmic-ray intensity and diurnal variations of air ion concentrations in different vegetation areas, in detail

Figure 2: (left) Seasonal correlation, of temperature change of atmosphere and cosmic-ray intensity in partially shielded chambers. A, temperature near ground; B, mean temperature up to 16 km, (right) Correlation of temperature change at Lindenberg with cosmic intensity at Potsdam. A, CR intensity; B, temperature near ground C, mean temperature up to 16 km [42]

Figure 3: (left) Fractal zeta zeros in nature and nanostructure laboratory: Plant, green trees under blue sky and (right) Plateaus in quantized Hall conductivity [From (left) Foto from Mamun Hossen, Han-Hsing Tu and Fiona Doan on unsplash.com (right) Wikipedia 'Quanten-Hall-Effekt']

Figure 4: Annual course of the Be activity concentration in the air near the ground. The circles represent the measured values of each month, the solid curve connects the monthly values averaged over almost six years and is therefore repeated periodically [43]

Holomorph $L(z, \chi)$, $\xi(z)$ in $z \approx \lambda$ describe a conductivity plateau as a non-radiative, non-turbulent, non-dissipative potential flow. A conductivity plateau is a plateau of constant temperature where transitions between plateaus cause temperature oscillations. Within the atmosphere global temperature oscillations are proven over 10^8 years as shown in Figure 9.

Figure 9. CRs (red) and global temperature (black) assumed from geochemical findings over $5 \cdot 10^8$ years from [24]

Figure 5-Diurnal Variation of air ions in Grapes vegetation area.

Figure 6-Diurnal variation of air ions in Chickpea vegetation area.

Figure 7- Diurnal Variation of air ions in Sugarcane vegetation area.

Figure 8- Diurnal variation of air ions in Onion vegetation area

Figure 5-8: Diurnal variation of measured air ion concentration near definite plants [26]

13. Conclusions

As a universe from nothing the zero-energy universe hypothesis proposes that the total amount of energy in the universe is exactly zero. These zero energies are implemented as one-dimensional zero of the Riemann zeta function. Dimensionless unified fields cover all orders of magnitude beyond local experimental setups. Iterated complex quadratic functions as lattices of algebraic units on elliptic curves support a universe as a quantum entangled fractal superfluid. A complex quadratic map written as real curvature $R_{\mu\nu}^4 + 2FR_{\mu\nu}^2 - G^2 = 0$ already enters the Friedmann equations. Viewing $R_{\mu\nu} = Rez_k$ as iterated, bifurcated tensile forces yields a matter state with charge and mass locally surrounded by a shower of 'CRs' and microwave excitations, in microstructures as well in the universe. An experimental support for a bifurcated spacetime is detected microwaves at QH as well air ionization in vegetation areas. Tensile forces of bifurcated spacetime are felt as CR and CMB. The zero-energy state of the universe described as a nontrivial zero of the Riemann zeta function and related Dirichlet L-functions is reduced to a holomorphic one-dimensional function. This allows to develop the fractal concept of the universe as a zero of $\zeta(z)$ contained in a zero of $\zeta(z)$ iteratively. The resulting Poisson equation allows to define a charge quantum by

solving DM by a 2^{2^k} -polar ball with a bifurcation tree of quadrupolar segments 1,2→1',2' of dashed lines as partial magnets. The segments dl_{xy} as a series in the geometric zeta function is the fractal analog of DM for large cloud (monopole) masses due to quadratic mass terms. However, a conductivity plateaus reflects a neutral-like quadrupole-like current as a holomorphic potential. Predicted second sound, CR, CMB at QH have low count rates which solve CCP $\rho_{exp} \neq \rho_{QS}$ by relating QS to a lap number of k-components. Highly correlated k-components as unstable orbits in the bifurcation tree explain QE by the CCP factor 2^{2^k} for k=9 or k=10. From the mathematical point of view binary substituted Dirichlet L- functions offer a new relation to quantum statistics.

14. References

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